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Understanding Function Shift of Representative Words based on the Analysis of “Attention” in Psychology¹

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Introduction

Understanding function shifts of representative words in scientific domains is essential for facilitating analysis of domain development status. During the process of research development, a word can have a quite different function from it was previously. For instance, by the 1990s, “selective-attention” was an emerging concept that facilitated new brain imaging discoveries, and nowadays it shifted to a technical terminology laying foundations for different research areas in Psychology. These new functions not only change the earlier role of the original word, but also reflect the dynamic evolution of a domain.

In previous work, domain development analysis is usually associated with real-time ascending/descending research trends (e.g., Zeb et al., 2021). However, the state of development of a domain cannot be fully embodied in the main two types of research trends. We need a systematic way of assessing a domain’s overall performance. Through the analysis of word function shifts, the current growth status and diversified research trends of a domain can be more grasped more comprehensively.

In this article, we assign functional roles to representative words of a domain feature word based on their shifts in semantics and information entropy over time. We treat the surrounding “environment” of words as complex rank-based lexical systems. By comparing the similarity ranking divergence of neighbouring words and considering the relative weights in neighbouring words’ ranking in different time periods, we study how words change meaning. Meanwhile, an information entropy-based strategy, which depicts the complexity of an application scenario, is adopted with the semantic shift to classify words as root words, trunk-

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branch words, green-leaf words, and dead-leaf words based on a hierarchical tree-like model. These help build a comprehensive understanding of the development status of a domain.

The domain feature word “Attention” in Psychology is selected for the case study in our study. Defined as an occupation taken by human consciousness, it is an important study aspect of mental activity and has been involved in research throughout the history of cognitive psychology. Current psychological research into attention influences an enormous range of fields ranging from mental health to artificial intelligence. As a complicated and changing feature word with long history and great influence, it is self-assured to be studied as a window into the development status of Psychology by addressing the task of understanding the role function shift of words.

Methodology

Data

We limit the source of our data to the psychology dataset of the database Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG), given the large-scale comprehensive coverage of scientific publications and the precise division of various disciplines. The dataset version used was published on April 17, 2019. Based on the growth trend of the literature shown in Figure 1, we roughly divide the development of the attention domain into four periods: latent period (1800-1970), germination period (1970-1984), growing period (1985-2004), and mature period (2005-2019). Excluding the latent period, we extracted 7,679,017 articles from 1970 to 2019 among all papers labelled “psychology”, a period when the body of literature in Psychology is increasing rapidly. The titles and abstracts of these articles are selected to be representative of the corpus of evolutionary Psychology.

Figure 1. Distribution of the number of publications in Psychology (1800-2019) in MAG

In order to generate sufficient data points for the subsequent temporal analyses, we set 5 years for the time span to group the literature data by equal time intervals. The pre-processing steps for word extraction are then performed in different chronological corpora. The text processing tools from Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) are utilized to tokenize, lemmatize, and filter stop words. Finally, after filtering out lemmas whose length is greater than 25 or less than 2 and lemmas containing non-alphabetic characters, the whole corpus contains all processed lemmas lowercased, stripped of punctuation.

Training Word Vectors

To identify representative neighbouring words of “attention”, simplified as “representative words”, we obtained word embeddings based on word2vec’s Skip-gram with Negative-sampling (SGNS) (Mikolov et al., 2013b) model, as it is robust to the task for discovering semantic shifts (Hamilton et al., 2016) and has the important function of using the target word to predict neighbouring words via randomly drawing ‘negative’ context word for each target word (Mikolov et al., 2013a).

We initially train embedding models with the Python library Gensim every five years. The input of the training model consists of the titles and abstracts of the selected papers. The output of the model contains vectors of words in each five-year period. Given the minimal number of words in a sentence is about 8, we set the context window of size 4 on each side for capturing the context of 1 word. Following the recommendations of Levy et al. (2015) in the parameter setting for embedding methods, we empirically set the negative sample prior α as $\log(5)$ and the embeddings of size 300.

Extracting neighbouring words of representative words

Representative words of attention-related studies are selected from the 1000 most similar words of the word “attention” based on cosine similarity in each period. In our study, the time-shifting word distributions of “attention” in vector space help identify words under similar research context with “attention”, which are deemed as representative words that has been studied in conjunction with “attention” in Psychology.

Having extracted representative words, we extract their neighbouring words in different time periods. The selection of neighbouring words serves to capture shifts in the semantics of the representative words to further understand changes in attention semantics and its related research over time.

Calculating information entropy of representative words

Information entropy (Shannon, 1948) can be a good measure of uncertainty in different application scenarios. For example, Philippatos and Wilson (1972) used entropy as a measure of the uncertainty of financial variables. To quantify the diversity and complexity of an application scenario, we use it to measure and compare the average amount of information of a keyword w in our psychology corpuses over all periods. The information entropy of a word during a certain time period is calculated as follow:

$$H(\mathbf{w}) = - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{f_{ij}}{\sum_{k \in j} f_{kj}} \log_2 \frac{f_{ij}}{\sum_{k \in j} f_{kj}} \quad (1)$$

where f_{ij} is the number of occurrences of a word i in a certain document j (here a document consists of a certain paper’s title and its abstract), $\sum_{k \in j} f_{kj}$ is the total number of words in document j , and n is the total number of documents in the corpus during a period. As the number of variables increases in a corpus, the level of uncertainty of a word raises, and the diversity and complexity of the usage scenario for words also increases. Under these circumstances, the word is considered more widespread than it was.

Calculating semantic shifting of representative words

Following previous studies, rank-turbulence divergence, a tunable instrument for comparing any two ranked lists of neighbouring words, is used to quantitatively measure semantic shift (Dodds et al., 2020). Since a neighbouring word τ has a rank $r_{(\tau,1)}$ in the semantic system R_I

and $r_{(\tau,2)}$ in the semantic system R_2 , we calculate the divergence between R_1 and R_2 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\alpha}^R(R_1 \parallel R_2) &= \sum_{\tau \in R_{1,2;\alpha}} \delta D_{\alpha,\tau}^R(R_1 \parallel R_2) \\ &= \frac{1}{N_{1,2;\alpha}} \frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha} \sum_{\tau \in R_{1,2;\alpha}} \left| \frac{1}{[r_{\tau,1}]^{\alpha}} - \frac{1}{[r_{\tau,2}]^{\alpha}} \right|^{1/(\alpha+1)} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} N_{1,2;\alpha} &= \frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha} \sum_{\tau \in R_1} \left| \frac{1}{[r_{\tau,1}]^{\alpha}} - \frac{1}{[N_1 + \frac{1}{2}N_2]^{\alpha}} \right|^{1/(\alpha+1)} \\ &\quad + \frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha} \sum_{\tau \in R_2} \left| \frac{1}{[N_2 + \frac{1}{2}N_1]^{\alpha}} - \frac{1}{[r_{\tau,2}]^{\alpha}} \right|^{1/(\alpha+1)} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where N_1 and N_2 are the number of distinct words in each ranked list of neighboring words, α ($0 \leq \alpha \leq \infty$) is a parameter to adjust the weights of the highly/lowly ranked neighboring words on the compound semantic system. According to the Pareto's principle, we tune α to make the divergence contributions of the top 20% of the neighbouring words account for 80% of the total divergence contributions D_{α}^R ($0 \leq D_{\alpha}^R \leq 1$) of the system. The higher the divergence, the greater the semantic shift between two time periods.

Implementing temporal analyses of semantic ranking divergence and entropy of representative words

We use the nonparametric Mann–Kendall trend test (Mann, 1945; Kossck & Kendall, 1950), a commonly used statistical test, to detect variation trends in word semantics and entropy over time based on the correlation between a rank order of a time series and its time sequence. We set the significance level as 0.05, which is a standard value for the significance test. In the series, each data value is compared to all subsequent data values. Let $\{x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_n\}$ represent data points, where x_i represents the n_{th} data point at time i . Then the Mann-Kendall statistic (S) is calculated as follows:

$$S = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{i=k+1}^n \text{sign}(x_i - x_k) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{sign}(x_i - x_k) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } (x_i - x_k) > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } (x_i - x_k) = 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } (x_i - x_k) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In Formula 4, a significantly high positive value of S (>0) indicates an increasing trend and a low negative value indicates a decreasing trend.

Results and Discussion

Understanding Temporal Development of Representative Words

To better track the dynamic evolving and overlap between representative words across the three development periods, we select some of them, which help untangle the topic development characters surrounding “attention” in each timespan after some manual selection by domain experts.

Figure 4. Temporal trend of divergence and entropy of root words (*Note: For each subfigure, the left and right vertical axes represent the divergence and entropy of the word, respectively; the same applies to Figures 6-8*).

Trunk-branch Words

Trunk-branch words are with great potential to expand one's research boundaries and generate unexpected research questions growing up like trunks and branches. They are identified by semantic divergence and entropy that do not monotonically increasing or decreasing, indicating their unexpected appearance.

For instance, although Broadbent's filter model of selective attention is a founding contribution to the "attention" domain, "broadbent" is not classified as a root word but as a growing trunk-branch word as more recent research has heatedly questioned its reliability and there is a growing upheaval surrounded with its original notion (e.g., Lachter et al. 2014; Treisman 1960).

Figure 5. Temporal trend of divergence and entropy of trunk-branch words

Young-leaf words

Young-leaf words indicating controversial “hot” issues that many scholars debate. They are characterized both by the increasing trends of entropy and semantic divergence, indicating the continuously diversifying application scenarios, and tremendously shifting semantics resulting from the new research content constantly available from heated discussions.

Figure 6. Temporal trend of divergence and entropy of young-leaf words

As the prevailing hypothesis in Linguistics saying goes, “words become semantically extended by being used in diverse contexts” (Winter et al. 2014). Taking “manifold” as an example, it can not only be used as a type of topological space correlating with spatio-temporal attention in Psychology, but also work in tandem with machine learning as a dimension reduction approach in Computer Science. If words frequently appear in various distinctive discipline backgrounds, the chances are high that they are going to be polysemous.

Under these circumstances, the variety and complexity of application scenarios is linked to the intrinsic nature of the semantic change. These two processes are likely to support and enhance each other, jointly creating new words, developing new scenarios, and fostering the success and prosperity of the domain.

Dead-leaf words

Dead-leaf words represent subjects in the process of becoming obsolete. They are characterized by the increasing trend of semantic divergence but the decreasing trend of entropy, indicating the unstable semantics lacking in usage flexibility and the gradually narrowing scope of application scenarios.

Figure 7. Temporal trend of divergence and entropy of dead-leaf words

As shown in Figure 7, their entropies remain well below average. These keywords are usually narrow and related to specific concepts. They are not evenly distributed among the field and gradually moving away from the interest of scholars. If no new research content emerges, they may even become extinct. For example, for “non-hyperactive”, there once have controversies on whether attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is an illness or behaviour at the extreme since the 1970s. As improved healthcare continues on deepening our knowledge, debate in the academic community is diminishing. As attention is considered one of the most thriving topics in psychology, the number of dead-leaf keywords in the field is relatively small. However, dead-leaf words are not bad characters, but normal “metabolic” parts during the domain life cycle.

Conclusion

By taking representative words of “attention” as an example, we study the shifting word function with the time passing to detect the development status of attention-related research under the psychology background. Taking into consideration both rank/importance and information entropy/usage scene complexity, we characterize the functionality of words as four types of tree parts, each of which alone or associated with “attention” is a representation of different growth states within the scientific domain.

From root words we can find concepts (e.g., selective-attention, crossmodal) laying the groundwork for future development; trunk-branch words (e.g., broadbent, socio-emotional) indicate research areas developing unpredictably; young-leaf words (e.g., manifold, two-process) suggests controversial topics hotly debated; dead-leaf words (e.g., non-hyperactive) demonstrate subjects becoming obsolete.

Our study expands traditional domain development analysis that usually only considered ascending/descending research trends to a multi-layered word function positioning analysis. From a hierarchical tree of words, we design a visual analysis framework that lays the foundation for a comprehensive and visual capture of a feature word's knowledge structure and development overtime, providing us with a fresh perspective on understanding domain development status. In the future, changes in word functions over different time periods will be examined to facilitate a better understanding of domain development from a dynamic perspective.

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